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Research Article

**MOLECULAR DETECTION OF RIFAMPICIN RESISTANCE
BY GENE EXPERT IN SUSPECTED PULMONARY TB CASES**¹Dr. Attiya Rasool, ²Dr. Laiqa Pervaiz, ³Dr. Syed Zubdha Ali Shah¹THQs Hospital Mailsi, Distt Vehari²District Headquarters Hospital, Sheikhpura³Aziz Fatimah Hospital, Faisalabad**Abstract:**

Worldwide control of TB is hindered by insensitive and slow indicative approaches, significantly for the exposure of drug-resistant systems and in those patients who have human immunodeficiency virus infection. Initial detection is vital to decline the rate of death and inter feretransmission, but the framework and difficulty require sensitive approaches to limit their effect and accessibility.

In this study, we assessed the performance of Chest X-Ray, Xpert MTB/RIF, which is defined as an automated molecular test specifically for (MTB) Mycobacterium Tuberculosis and resistance to (RIF) rifampin. on positive cases first with microscopy and X-RAY Chest, ESR and then do the Xpert MTB/RIF, (a molecular test for "Mycobacterium tuberculosis" and RIF (resistance to Rifampin)), with completely unified sample processing about 1730 patients with suspected multidrug-resistant or drug-sensitivity pulmonary TB. Data has been gathered through PubMed Database for eligible patients of four different countries. There were two specimens who processed through sodium hydroxide and n-acetyl-L-cysteine before microscopy, MTB/RIF test and for one specimen was utilized for direct testing through MTB/RIF test and microscopy.

In between the culture-positive patients, a particular, direct MTB/RIF test analyzed smear-positive tuberculosis in 551 of 561 patients (98.2%) and smear-negative tuberculosis in 124 of 171 patients (72.5%). This specific test analyzed that 604 out of 609 patients (99.2%) are without TB. Patients with smear-negative, culture-positive TB, the second MTB/RIF additional test improved sensitivity by 12.6% points and according to the third test, this sensitivity increased by 5.1% points to a 90.2% total. According to a comparison with phenotypic drug-susceptibility testing, MTB/RIF examine correct identification of, 200 from 205 patients, Rifampin-resistant bacteria and 98.1% (504 of 514) patients with Rifampin sensitive bacteria. Abovementioned tests stipulated sensitive detection of rifampin resistance and tuberculosis bluntly from basic sputum in less than two hours.

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INTRODUCTION:

According to reports, the drug-susceptibility testing is available by only 1.37 million patients who have TB co-infection with HIV. Diagnostic interruption, aggravated through the inconsistent frequency of smear-negative disease in HIV associated TB, in general. The fiasco to swiftly treat and recognized affected patients indicates to increase in secondary resistance, mortality and ongoing transmission. The mycobacterial cultural complexity and amplification of current nucleic acid technologies for the recognition of TB and multidrug-resistant tuberculosis detection and the requirement for the linked framework restrict the use of similar reference laboratories tests (Dayal *et al.*, 2017).

While responding to the latest requirement for rapid and simple analyses tools at the treatment point in those countries which have the high burden; a completely automated molecular test for drug-resistance testing and TB case detection was formed. Accordingly, chest X-RAY and Xpert MTB/RIF, "Mycobacterium TB automated molecular test and resistance to rifampin (RF)" utilizes heminested real-time PCR "polymerase chain reaction" assay to elevate an MTB-specific *rpoB* gene particular sequence, which also investigated with mutations molecular beacons inside the rifampin-resistance fortitude region (Guenauoui *et al.*, 2016).

The examination is carried out on the MTB/RIF test proposal, which integrates PCR in a specific disposable plastic cartridge comprising all substances vital for nucleic acid extraction, bacterial lysis, amplicon and amplification detection. In this examination, the only manual step is the addition of a bactericidal buffer to sputum earlier totransferringa described volume to the cartridge. The MTB/RIF cartridge is particularly inserted into the device of Gene Xpert, which delivers outputs within two hours (Guled *et al.*, 2016).S

METHODS:

Study Population

This study is based from July 2008 to March 2009 (for the period of eight months), we gathered data from PubMed Database, from four different countries. According to the PubMed Database, there was an enrolment of sequential adults in four different countries, with suggestive symptoms of pulmonary TB or multidrug-resistant TB who can give three sputum specimen of 1.5 ml. In a group of patients, pulmonary TB risk was qualified only if they had not taken TB medicine within the last sixty days, therefore the multidrug-resistance disease group included with those patients who had

experience of any last treatment.

Study Design and Oversight

Data for this research were collected through the PubMed Database; accordingly the statistical assessments were performed through SPSS.

Laboratory Methods

Patients meet the clinical criteria of eligibility were inquired to give three sputum samples over a 2 daytime. According to a random fashion, 2 of 3 specimens were administered with *sodium hydroxide* and *N-acetyl-1-l-cysteine*, trailed by centrifugation and then were resuspended in 1.5 milliliters of phosphate subjected and buffer to microscopy with Ziehl-Neelsen, cultivation and staining on solid medium, with the liquid medium [mycobacteria development indicator tube, BACTECMGIT] 960 Culture; BD Systems of Microbiology) use, and the test of MTB/RIF. The 3rd sputum specimen was analyzed by Ziehl-Neelsen microscopy and test of MTB/RIF without decontamination of NALC-NaOH (Dayal *et al.*, 2017).

According to PubMed Database reports, the initial positive culture from every sample practice validation of *M. Tuberculosis* classes by MPT64 antigen recognition (Capilia TB Laboratories) and testing of indirect drug susceptibility with the method of proportion for two countries' sites, first in Lima Durban and secondly in Cape Town, as mentioned in PubMed Database. For these specific sites, testing of conventional nucleic acid-amplification was finalized on DNA which was basically extracted from the centrifugation pallet of NALC-NaOH of the 1st sputum specimen with Cobas Amplicor MTB (Roche) use, under the instructions of the manufacturer. On these sites, the line-probe assay has been used for drug-resistant genotyping with the utilization of the Geno-type MTBDR plus assay, accomplished from culture isolates or from the pellet of NALC-NaOH of the second sputum sample, under the complete instructions of the manufacturer (Dayal *et al.*, 2017).

A repeat of TB analysis was accomplished in patients who had culture-negative and smear-negative samples if another nucleic acid-amplification test or MTB/RIF was positive. The concluding diagnosis for those patients who were experiencing repeat analysis was performed on the basis of clinical information and conventional laboratory outputs by the committees of clinical review, as per mentioned in PubMed Database. HIV outputs were acquired by the review of clinical records and also accessible for only a subcategory of patients.

Analysis Categories

Basically, patients were further divided into 4 categories for assessment: those with culture positive and smear-positive pulmonary TB; culture-positive pulmonary TB; those with smear-negative; and those with no bacteriologic indication of TB, who significantly improved without any TB treatment; and finally those which were culture-negative and smear-negative pulmonary TB. There was a smear-positive case recognized as at least 2 smears of revealing grade (from 0 to 10 acid-fast bacilli per 100/fields) (Guenaoui *et al.*, 2016).

Accordingly, as positive outputs, a culture-positive case also described on 1 of 4 culture vials. Due to a clear and final diagnosis was asked, those patients having an indeterminate analysis were not included from the main assessment if there found a negative culture output while patient obtaining TB medication, 3 of 4 cultural contaminations, susceptibility of indeterminate phenotypic rifampin, non-tuberculous mycobacterial growth, positive sputum smear's negative culture or supposed cross-cultural contamination (which is 1 of 4 culture had output positively after >28 days to development in MGIT (Guled *et al.*, 2016).

MTB/RIF TEST

MTB/RIF test was performed by two operators generally known to be laboratory technicians. They were qualified for this after running four tests each. There was a ratio of 2:1 of untreated sputum to which a sample reagent was added while 3:1 ratio contributed to the decontaminated sputum pellets. The volume requirement was to meet the additional sample reagents for the assay sample. However, for the first 15 minutes, at room temperature, 2ml of inactivated material was introduced in the test cartridge in a closed sputum container. ("0.5ml-0.7ml of decontaminated pellet or untreated sputum"). In a laboratory space and microscopy space, the cartridges were introduced in the test platform. The results were electronic and were transferred to the central database from the MTB/RIF test system (Smith, 2017).

Sequencing

Bidirectional sequencing was achieved on the "81-bp *rpoB* primary region of culture isolates" in discordant strains and all rifampin-resistant with reverse and forward primers with the utilization of the "BigDye Terminator Cycle Sequencing Kit".

(Source: Smith, 2018)

Statistical Analysis

For a single direct test, the MTB/RIF tests were reviewed considering their sensitivity and particularity. For this, three tests were defined; on a single pelleted sample, a combination of two tests which consisted of one direct and one pelleted sample, combinations of three tests which included one direct and two pelleted samples. The test was categorized as positive even if only one result was marked positive. All the results carrying a label of showing error, no result or invalid were discarded. In some cases, where the limited samples were enough to provide a result, the assays were repeated on the same people and those results were then used as analysis. Wilson's binomial method having ("95% confidence level") was used in order to assess the single direct test or combination of tests. In cases, where comparisons among groups or testing methods were involved, in the account for within-patient clustering, the generalized estimating equations were used (Smith, 2017).

Table 1
(Clinical Characteristics of Patients)

Variable	Lima, Peru (N=341)	Baku, Azerbaijan (N = 353)	Cape Town, South Africa (N = 380)	Durban, South Africa (N = 346)	Mumbai, India (N = 310)	All Patients (N = 1730)
Demographic or clinical characteristic						
Median age (range) — yr	31 (18-79)	37 (20-69)	36 (18-80)	32 (18-68)	30 (17-88)	34 (17-88)
Female sex — no./total no. (%)	138/319 (43.3)	0/251	119/349 (34.1)	186/313 (59.4)	90/230 (39.1)	533/1462 (36.5)
HIV infection — no./total no. (%)	3/179 (1.7)	9/193 (4.7)	159/209 (76.1)	21/73 (28.8)	4/91 (4.4)	39/2976 (40.2)
History of tuberculosis — no./total no. (%)	75/316 (23.7)	137/251 (54.6)	148/344 (43.0)	138/306 (45.1)	173/230 (75.2)	671/1447 (46.4)
Diagnosis group at enrollment						
Suspicion of pulmonary tuberculosis — no./total no. (%)	293/341 (85.9)	131/353 (37.1)	223/380 (58.7)	272/346 (78.6)	91/310 (29.4)	1010/1730 (58.4)
Suspicion of multidrug-resistant tuberculosis not receiving therapy — no./total no. (%)	41/341 (12.0)	149/353 (42.2)	136/380 (35.8)	59/346 (17.1)	60/310 (19.4)	445/1730 (25.7)
Suspicion of multidrug-resistant tuberculosis receiving therapy — no./total no. (%)	7/341 (2.1)	73/353 (20.7)	21/380 (5.5)	15/346 (4.3)	159/310 (51.3)	275/1730 (15.9)
Distribution in final diagnostic category						
Smear- and culture-positive tuberculosis — no./total no. (%)	199/341 (58.4)	80/353 (22.7)	96/380 (25.3)	30/346 (8.7)	162/310 (52.3)	567/1730 (32.8)
Smear-negative and culture-positive tuberculosis — no./total no. (%)	12/341 (3.5)	69/353 (19.5)	52/380 (13.7)	15/346 (4.3)	26/310 (8.4)	174/1730 (10.1)
Clinical tuberculosis — no./total no. (%)	6/341 (1.8)	32/353 (9.1)	12/380 (3.2)	49/346 (14.2)	6/310 (1.9)	105/1730 (6.1)
No tuberculosis — no./total no. (%)	102/341 (29.9)	70/353 (19.8)	189/380 (49.7)	219/346 (63.3)	36/310 (11.6)	616/1730 (35.6)
Indeterminate — no./total no. (%)	22/341 (6.5)	102/353 (28.9)	31/380 (8.2)	33/346 (9.5)	80/310 (25.8)	268/1730 (15.5)
Culture-negative disease with suspected multidrug resistance receiving therapy						
Contamination of ≥3 of 4 cultures	0/22	28/102 (27.5) [†]	0/31	0/33	0/80	28/268 (10.4)
Single culture positive with >28 days (MGIT) or <20 colonies (LJ)	0/22	0/102	3/31 (9.7)	2/33 (6.1)	2/80 (2.5)	7/268 (2.6)
Smear-positive, culture-negative tuberculosis						
Smear-positive, culture-negative tuberculosis	14/22 (63.6)	5/102 (4.9)	4/31 (12.9)	12/33 (36.4)	4/80 (5.0)	39/268 (14.6)
Non-tuberculous mycobacteria only	2/22 (9.1)	4/102 (3.9)	1/31 (3.2)	2/33 (6.1)	14/80 (17.5)	23/268 (8.6)
Discrepant phenotypic drug-susceptibility testing	2/22 (9.1)	5/102 (4.9)	2/31 (6.5)	0/33	1/80 (1.3)	10/268 (3.7)
Death or loss to follow-up	2/22 (9.1)	9/102 (8.8)	18/31 (58.1)	7/33 (21.2)	10/80 (12.5)	46/268 (17.2)

(Source: Smith, 2018)

RESULTS:**Patients**

Total patients were 1730 from which 1462 patients/samples were finalized for analysis while 268 patients excluded due to different reasons. The level of the patients suffering from smear and culture-positive tuberculosis was 567 ("38.8 %") whereas 174 ("11.9 %") had smear-negative, culture-positive tuberculosis. Moreover, 105 ("7.2%") were diagnosed with clinical tuberculosis; 616 ("42.1 %") had no evidence of tuberculosis, also mentioned in Table 1. Perhaps, 113 patients were refused for testing due to incomplete sample count of sputum during the test, out of which 103 patients were missing and 10 patients' samples were missing. Due to many adequate reasons, 268 patients were discarded from the analysis. This was merely due to culture-negative samples (115 patients), but still were facing the multidrug resistance due to tuberculosis treatment (Patil, 2017).

Sensitivity and Specificity**Case Detection**

The sensitivity rate of 97.6% was evaluated during the MTB/RIF Test in the patients of culture-positive tuberculosis. 90.2% sensitivity was resulted for smear-negative whereas 99.8% for smear- and culture-positive cases were noted with minimum change in sensitivity was seen. (“P = 0.24 by chi-square test”) as mentioned in Table 2.

Table 2

(Overall Specificity and Sensitivity of MTB/RIF Test, as per the number of Tests per Patient and compared with 3 Smears and 4 Cultures)

Site and No. of Tests	Sensitivity			Specificity
	All Culture-Positive	Smear-Positive and Culture-Positive	Smear-Negative and Culture-Positive	No Tuberculosis
Site				
Lima, Peru				
Correct — no./total no. (%)	209/211 (99.1)	199/199 (100)	10/12 (83.3)	102/102 (100)
95% CI	96.6–99.7	98.1–100.0	55.2–95.3	96.4–100.0
Baku, Azerbaijan				
Correct — no./total no. (%)	144/149 (96.6)	80/80 (100.0)	64/69 (92.8)	68/70 (97.1)
95% CI	92.4–98.6	95.4–100.0	84.1–96.9	90.2–99.2
Cape Town, South Africa				
Correct — no./total no. (%)	142/148 (95.9)	95/96 (99.0)	47/52 (90.4)	186/189 (98.4)
95% CI	91.4–98.1	94.3–99.8	79.4–95.8	95.4–99.5
Durban, South Africa				
Correct — no./total no. (%)	43/45 (95.6)	30/30 (100.0)	13/15 (86.7)	213/219 (97.3)
95% CI	85.2–98.8	88.6–100.0	62.1–96.3	94.2–98.7
Mumbai, India				
Correct — no./total no. (%)	185/188 (98.4)	162/162 (100.0)	23/26 (88.5)	35/36 (97.2)
95% CI	95.4–99.5	99.7–100.0	71.0–96.0	85.8–99.5
No. of MTB/RIF tests				
3 Samples (2 pellet and 1 direct)				
Correct — no./total no. (%)	723/741 (97.6)	566/567 (99.8)	157/174 (90.2)	604/616 (98.1)
95% CI	96.2–98.5	99.0–100.0	84.9–93.8	96.6–98.9
2 Samples (1 pellet and 1 direct)				
Correct — no./total no. (%) [†]	1423/1482 (96.0)	1127/1134 (99.4)	296/348 (85.1)	1215/1232 (98.6)
95% CI	94.6–97.1	98.6–99.7	79.7–89.2	97.5–99.2
1 Sample (direct)				
Correct — no./total no. (%)	675/732 (92.2)	551/561 (98.2)	124/171 (72.5)	604/609 (99.2)
95% CI	90.0–93.9	96.8–99.0	65.4–78.7	98.1–99.6

(Source: Smith, 2018)

Due to multiple tests, a single assay was given for sputum; however, a modest effect was seen due to the testing of multiple specimens. About 92.2% culture-confirmed tuberculosis was noted in the single direct test which increased to 96.0% when the additional pelleted sample was tested in the MTB/RIF test, according to abovementioned Table 1. Moreover, The digits evaluated in the testing of the assay was 72.5% for one test, 85.1% for two tests and 90.2% for

three tests in the smear- negative, culture-positive tuberculosis. Additionally, a Lowenstein-Jensen culture showed lower proportions of results for patients than in the MTB/RIF test. Considering HIV, the HIV-positive patients had a mark of 93.9% of pulmonary tuberculosis whereas the HIV-negative patients showed 98.4% result. (“P = 0.02”). Lastly, the results were eventually same for the decontaminated pellet and untreated sputum (“P=

0.16”)(Lee and Chee, 2018).

For a single direct MTB/RIF test, 99.2% specificity resulted; for two MTB/RIF tests, 98.6% was reported whereas, in three MTB/RIF tests, 98.1% was reported. Also, from the sputum pellets, the DNA was extracted for alternative nucleic acid-amplification testing. In this testing, the rate of sputum was lower than ProbeTec (“83.7% vs. 83.9%, $P=0.96$ ”) whereas it was higher than Amplicor, (“94.6% vs. 86.8%, $P<0.01$ ”). The specificity of MTB/RIF tests didn’t show any variations with Probetec or Amplicor(Lee and Chee, 2018).

Considering the global issues, *rpoB* types of mutations were included in the study. However, 16 different types of mutations identified resistant strains with 516, 526 and 531 codon numbers. Patients suffering from culture-negative tuberculosis which showed multi-drug resistance, a total of 115

patients were reported. Out of these, 8 were detected with rifampin and 51 patients showed positive results of MTB/RIF tests. The 8 patients with abnormality were then transferred for second-line therapy for the treatment as the doctors were primarily unaware of the MTB/RIF test results. No patients which although showed positive results on MTB/RIF testing, had no resistance with rifampin and so were not advised for secondary therapy. The MTB/RIF tests could be used by everyone facing the tuberculosis issue. Also, this test could detect the patients receiving multi-drug resistance, culture conversion and therapies related to the diagnosis(Lee and Chee, 2018).

Detection of Multidrug Resistance

As shown in Table 3, the specificity and sensitivity of the MTB/RIF test done for multi-drug resistance and rifampin detection.

Table 3

Site and Total	Phenotypic Drug-Susceptibility Testing [†]		Phenotypic Drug-Susceptibility Testing and Discrepant Resolution by Sequencing [‡]	
	Sensitivity for Rifampin Resistance	Specificity for Rifampin Resistance	Sensitivity for Rifampin Resistance	Specificity for Rifampin Resistance
Lima, Peru — no./total no. (%)	16/16 (100.0)	190/193 (98.4)	19/19 (100.0)	190/190 (100.0)
Baku, Azerbaijan — no./total no. (%)	47/49 (95.9)	90/94 (95.7)	51/52 (98.1)	90/90 (100.0)
Cape Town, South Africa — no./total no. (%)	15/16 (93.8)	126/126 (100.0)	15/15 (100.0)	126/126 (100.0)
Durban, South Africa — no./total no. (%)	3/3 (100.0)	38/38 (100.0)	3/3 (100.0)	38/38 (100.0)
Mumbai, India — no./total no. (%)	119/121 (98.3)	61/64 (95.3)	121/122 (99.2)	62/62 (100.0)
Total for rifampin resistance				
Correct — no./total no. (%)	200/205 (97.6)	505/515 (98.1)	209/211 (99.1)	506/506 (100.0)
95% CI — %	94.4–99.0	96.5–98.9	96.6–99.7	99.2–100.0
Total for multidrug resistance				
Correct — no./total no. (%)	195/200 (97.5)		197/199 (99.0)	
95% CI — %	94.3–98.9		96.4–99.7	

(Source: Smith, 2018)

For 15 out of 718 patients for who outputs on the test of MTB/RIF were discrepant on phenotypic testing and sequencing established resistant-linked *rpoB* changes in nine types that were analyzed as “testing of rifampin-sensitive on drug susceptibility”, regulated the wild-type allele presence in one type deemed testing of rifampin-resistant on drug susceptibility. Accordingly, it also analyzed three patients which varied infection having wild-type and distorted strains in the same culture. From 209 of 211 patients, MTB/RIF test correctly noticed rifampin resistance (ratio 99.1% sensitivity).

Indeterminate Rate

The results were indefinite showing only 192 of total

tests performed from 5190 tests with (“3.7 %”) rate which was lower than Lowenstein-Jensen Cultures (“ $P<0.001$ ”) and with the culture-contamination rate of “381 from 6920 MGIT”, (“5.5 %”). In case of repeating the tests, the results dropped to 63 of 5190 tests with (“1.2 %”) drop rate. However, the repeat rates which showed reliable results was “129 of 139 tests”, (“92.8 %”). No unusual results were seen during the tests. For rifampin resistance, the outlay of positive results was “20 of 2072 samples” with (“1.0 %”) incidence rate. While, in smear-negative, culture-positive sputum samples, a very slow result was seen which took almost 35-37 cycles during the MTB/RIF test? At this time, a new software was also introduced which exempted all the incomplete or

same results which made the function easier, for example, out of 40 cycles, 19-20 cycles were indefinite with quick and reliable results of the assay at the end(Lee and Chee, 2018).

DISCUSSION:

In the study, the results of pulmonary tuberculosis and rifampin resistance screening were detected in low-income countries as a point-of-treatment of an assay. A total of 97% were successfully diagnosed with culture-confirmed tuberculosis with 90% of people facing smear-negative disease. The performances were suggested to be widely applicable of rifampin resistance detection and discrimination. As the results of HIV infection and tuberculosis were low; some sites were consulted in order to improve the results. The results improved to 60-80% in general(MATEE, MFINANGA and HOLM-HANSEN, 2016).

In order to generalize the results, it was researched that it might be possible that the results would not primarily be the same. This was due to the reference facilities which were used and it was difficult to produce such results again. Replication of health posts, microscopy centers, and electricity supply and point-of-treatment settings at room temperature was reported to be difficult(Lee and Chee, 2018).

Secondly, usage of sophisticated technology was used due to which the cost-effectiveness was low for the MTB/RIF tests. Due to higher costs, FIND was consulted for reducing the costs of the instruments used and tests which could produce more reliable results than microscopy and also help in attaining good results available in countries easily(MATEE, MFINANGA, and HOLM-HANSEN, 2016).

CONCLUSION:

As a conclusion, it is stated that the probability of tuberculosis detection and the rise of multi-drug resistance and how changes in drugs may change the health conditions. Moreover, awareness was created among different cultures in order to expand the know-how of the diseases. The main issue identified was the mismanagement of the personnel available, missing of the instruments, unavailability of the health centers or poor workings in the settings which produced results in 4-5 months reducing the effectiveness. Also, one of the complications seen is the difficulty of standard nucleic acid amplification which hinders to improve and promote. A little chance of amplicon contamination is seen as during the MTB/RIF test as the extracted, amplified and detected data is not opened after getting into the test cartridge. This problem is leading to the

ineffectiveness of the results.

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